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Perceptions, profiles and regulatory challenges regarding Hate Speech in Spanish Youth Gaming Culture

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Conflict of interest

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Supplementary Materials

The final survey can be accessed through the URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10405550>

The final database of the analyzed data can be accessed through the URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10409790>

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Abstract

Introduction: Massively multiplayer online video games (MMO) have emerged as significant platforms for social interaction among youth and in environments conducive to hate speech. This study examines the perceptions, profiles, and factors associated with hate speech in MMO among young Spanish individuals and the regulatory and social challenges they present.

Method: An online survey was conducted between October and November 2023, including 1,436 young people aged 16–29 years who participated in the MMO. **Results:** Over 60% of the participants perceived a low or moderate prevalence of hate speech in MMO, acknowledging its impact on vulnerable groups based on race, religion, sexual orientation, and ideology. A widespread perception of impunity was also observed in these digital environments, which facilitated the normalization of hate speech. **Conclusions:** Findings underscore the need for more effective and collaborative public policies to regulate MMO, enhance media literacy, and facilitate prosocial interactions among adolescents and young adults.

Keywords: hate speech, violence, youth, Internet, digital communication, Video games, policies

Submitted version

Introduction

Hate speech in today's digital space has garnered increasing attention from social and academic perspectives (Wright, Wachs & Guadix, 2021). To date, there is no consensus on the meaning of hate speech; it is often associated with similar but distinct terms such as uncivil, hateful, abusive, offensive, or violent expressions (Esau, 2021). They share two common characteristics: public nature and the intent to harm a specific group or member. However, they differ in how much they violate the social, educational, and legal norms established in each society (Struck, 2019).

Hate speech is intended to incite hatred against individuals or social groups based on factors such as ethnicity, gender, nationality, religion, sexual orientation, and ideology (Struck, 2019).

Massive multiplayer online platforms (MMO) have become conducive to the spread of hate speech in digital environments. With anonymity and global reach, these platforms attract extremist groups aiming to propagate antisocial behaviour and establish their narratives (Aguerri, Santisteban & Miró-Llinares, 2023; Wells et al., 2023). They have evolved into entertainment, communication, and socialization forms, particularly for young people active in digital environments, such as video games (Romo et al., 2023).

A sector expected to experience revenue growth in the coming years (AEVI, 2022; Arias, 2023). Video game consumption among individuals aged 16–29 years is expected to reach 65% of this demographic in Spain by 2022. The average time spent playing games on PCs, tablets, consoles, smartphones, and handheld consoles exceeded seven hours per week (AEVI, 2022). The massively multiplayer online game, or MMO (e.g., Call of Duty, Fortnite, Apex Legends), is a growing modality in the video game industry. MMO spans several genres and enables participants to play with others or individually in online virtual worlds (Raith et al., 2021).

Globally, there is an increasing trend toward greater digital platform regulation due to concerns about their market power, data privacy, and spreading disinformation and hate content (Flew & Su, 2023). In this context, MMO social advancement and its challenges have prompted countries to implement measures to develop public policies to regulate these platforms. This is because of their social nature and the potential for propagating harmful messages facilitated by interactions and user-generated content across online games. A primary challenge is balancing freedom of expression, economic interests, public values, user rights protection, and the need to mitigate harmful content that may incite violence and discrimination in the real world (Cammaerts & Mansell, 2020; Meissner, 2022). The rapid evolution of online social platforms has further exacerbated this challenge.

Policies to regulate MMO have been implemented at regional and national levels. However, significant differences and challenges exist, depending on the approach adopted. Regions and countries like the European Union, Spain, China, and the United Kingdom focus on developing regulatory mechanisms to protect young individuals and those with high-risk behaviours like gambling addiction. These initiatives include promoting collaborative regulatory approaches and measures such as limiting economic losses, restricting payment methods for at-risk players, protecting against illegal content and rights violations affecting mental health, limiting online game usage for minors, and implementing stringent identity verification systems to restrict access (Schlesinger, 2022; Ministry of Social Rights, Consumption and Agenda 2030 of Spain, 2023; European Commission, 2022; Fernández, Sora & Comas, 2023).

The implemented regulations promote collaborative approaches among regulatory entities, foster competition for businesses associated with social platforms like MMO, and seek flexible mechanisms enabling regulators to respond to technological advancements and

encourage platform self-regulation (Cusumano, Gawer & Yoffie, 2021; Schlesinger, 2022; Fletcher, 2023).

Scholars emphasize the challenges regulatory frameworks face in adapting to the rapid technological evolution of these platform types (Kokshagina, Reinecke & Karanasios, 2023). These include the lack of a unified regulatory standard, which causes fragmentation and complicated implementation (Trachtman, 2023). Political silos and concessions between governments and corporations have impeded solutions for establishing frameworks to govern platforms such as MMO and their data (Popiel, 2022). Monopolistic tendencies within the sector have been observed (Fletcher, 2023), as has the complexity of moderating user-generated content (Mezei, 2022). The challenge is worsened by platforms using hybrid moderation strategies that combine human and automated methods, often failing to detect sophisticated hate speech that targets individuals or groups (Munn, 2020; DeCook et al., 2022).

Implementing punitive measures and structural changes can mitigate hate speech in digital environments (DeCook et al., 2022). This promotes shared responsibility among governments, platforms, and users and enhances transparency in moderation practices (DeCook et al., 2022). These interventions could improve the efficacy of regulations combating hate messages toward vulnerable individuals or groups in MMO. Liu, Luo and Lu (2023) identified a negative correlation between this expression and regulatory measures.

Understanding young individuals' perceptions, influencing variables, and profiles regarding hate speech in Massively Multiplayer Online (MMO) games is crucial for developing a framework for current regulatory policies. This ensures a regulatory and usage environment for MMO games that prevent their exploitation in disseminating hate messages. Fostering positive interactions, moral commitment and personal responsibility among young individuals is essential to counteracting hate speech (Ieracitano et al., 2023). It is imperative

to incorporate media literacy training, empathy development, and adherence to social norms among young users. Public policies must promote initiatives to combat hate in digital environments by encouraging diverse perspectives, establishing clear participation rules, implementing regulatory measures against non-compliance, and ensuring accountability for content hosted on these platforms (Wachs et al., 2022).

Salen-Tekinbaş (2020) asserted that MMOs facilitate prosocial behaviours among young individuals through collaborative activities in digital entertainment environments. This promotes belonging, friendship, and social learning via interactions and communication tools, including in-game chats, forums, and community platforms such as Discord and Instagram, which connect meta-gaming ecosystems.

Other authors have emphasized that prolonged engagement in MMO activities can adversely affect young people's health (addiction), mental well-being (cognition and emotions), and social health (relationships and interactions) (Raith et al., 2021). Normalizing hate speech and aggression in digital spaces is a growing concern for society and academia (Costello, Rukus & Hawdon, 2019). Donoso, Rubio and Vilà (2018), and Wachs et al. (2022) found that many young people in the United States (53%), Finland (48%), the United Kingdom (39%), and Spain (68%) have been exposed.

Due to reduced inhibition, Udris (2014) indicated that young individuals are aware of impunity in MMO environments. Unlike in-person settings, this disinhibition fosters "freedom" in self-expression and interaction, resulting in positive or toxic effects. Exposure to hate speech intended to insult, degrade, or threaten can be mitigated through coping strategies, such as retaliating, seeking family support, using blocking techniques, and obtaining professional help from police or helplines (Gámez-Guadix, Wachs & Wright, 2020). The techniques vary according to age, sex, and socioeconomic background (Wachs et al., 2020).

Literature review

Research has shown that MMO are key platforms for recruiting and radicalizing extreme right-wing groups. Studies by Koehler, Fiebig, and Jugl (2022) highlight that social and emotional bonds in gaming foster an environment conducive to intense radicalization, influencing offline behaviour.

MMO users, whether perpetrators, victims, or witnesses, are aware of hate in digital environments (Cáceres-Zapatero, Brändle & Paz-Rebollo, 2023). This awareness stems from personal experiences spreading such messages, the normalization of which may boost their prevalence in similar demographics. This is significant considering the intersection between participants' cultural identity and gaming culture when disseminating narratives (Wells et al., 2023). This process can occur subtly or overtly, leveraging MMO anonymity, community bonds formed through shared gaming experiences (Koehler, Fiebig & Jugl, 2022), and the serial nature of video game narratives, which makes hate expressions linked to extreme political ideologies more appealing and rapidly spread (Leitch, 2023). This may catalyze the radicalization of marginalized players exposed to hate speech.

Primary approaches to studying hate speech and harassment in video games include addressing the presence of hate speech and involvement of extreme ideological groups (Conway, Scrivens, & McNair, 2019), normalizing these groups' beliefs and recruitment strategies (Davey, 2021), identifying harassment forms in online gaming communities (Kowert et al., 2022), and mapping profiles and motivations of hate promoters in digital environments (Wachs & Wright, 2018; Wells et al., 2023). The effectiveness of moderation systems in controlling this behaviour has also been explored (Brown & Hennis, 2019). Research on the intersection of hate and video games has focused on analyzing message

content, player behaviour, community dynamics, and the social impact of extreme ideologies in these digital spaces (Wells et al., 2023).

Kowert et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of considering the historical contexts of hate speech in video game cultures and the link between player identity and game culture in promoting extreme ideologies. This hostility can create an antagonistic atmosphere, affecting the mental well-being and identity formation of users targeted by race, religion, sexual orientation, ideology, and other factors (Cover, 2022).

Studies by Wachs and Wright (2018), Melović et al. (2020), and Wells et al. (2023) identified factors influencing the recognition of hate speech victims and perpetrators. Key variables included age, education, ideology, online activity, perceived disinhibition, and gender. Perpetrators reveal identities and spend more time online, whereas victims are less active and cautious about sharing data.

In Spain, studies on hate and harassment in video games have examined cyber-hate prevalence, its impact on mental well-being, and sociopolitical factors shaping gaming environments. These studies highlight the complexity of hating gaming and the need for effective strategies. Research by Gámez-Guadix, Wachs and Wright (2020), Zych and Llorent (2021), and Ojeda et al. (2023) identifies primary targets of digital hate as race, religion, sexual orientation, and ideology. Coping strategies, profiles of hate speech victims and perpetrators, and hostility dynamics are evident in digital contexts, such as video games. Aguerri, Santisteban, and Miró-Llinares (2023) reported toxic behaviour is prevalent in games like "League of Legends," mainly by a small group of users. Planells (2020) linked video games to users' sociocultural contexts, highlighting risks such as anxiety, impulsiveness, and social skill deficits that exacerbate hatred and toxicity.

A Spanish study by Martínez-Ferrer et al. (2021), Lemercier-Dugarin et al. (2021), and Nogueira-López et al. (2023) suggest that aggressive behaviour in MMO is influenced by

factors like age, gender, socio-environmental conditions (e.g., parental controls, family structures), and gaming motivations. These studies indicate that gaming aggression is linked to broader patterns of aggression and impulsivity, with young men showing a higher prevalence of such behaviours.

Victimization of digital gaming is linked to age, gender, and gaming habits. Young individuals, particularly women, are most affected by hostility. Women are more likely to acknowledge this issue, whereas men engage more deeply. Increased gaming hours correlated with higher victimization rates in MMO.

Few studies have focused on witnesses, but Wachs and Wright (2018) suggest a correlation between witnesses and perpetrators, indicating that witnesses are likelier to become perpetrators. This aligns with social learning theory (Akers et al., 1979), which posits that young people imitate accepted behaviours. The normalization of hate speech in online gaming can desensitize individuals. The authors highlighted the need for more research on the factors associated with individuals who experience, perpetrate, or witness hate speech, given the complexity of understanding each role's motivation and background. Studying social learning in MMO is valuable, particularly in user engagement in digital environments. Normalizing hate speech can lead to negative observational learning as users may replicate harmful behaviours that seem unpunished (Nakawake & Kobayashi, 2022). This favours increased aggressiveness and decreased prosocial behaviour (Greitemeyer, 2022).

Despite progress in the study of hate in MMO, challenges persist, justifying further research. The complex nature of online interactions and hate incitement, including jargon and implicit language (Cohen et al., 2023), complicates detection in digital scenarios. MMO studies have shown that estimating user profiles is crucial for combating hostility and toxicity. Effective profiling of perpetrators, victims, and witnesses is essential, considering the contextual nature of hate promotion (Ahmed et al., 2022). This can advance more precise

and impartial systems for hate detection and prevention (Hatfield et al., 2022) and promote a safer gaming environment through behavioural standards, fostering positive interactions (Tomkinson & Van den Ende, 2022).

Methods

This study aimed to analyze the profiles of young people in Spain and their perceptions of hate speech messages in MMO. To this end, we establish the following specific objectives (SO):

- SO1: Establish the characteristics that shape young people's perceptions of hate speech in video games.
- SO2: Identify the variables that influence young people's perceptions of the presence of hate speech in video games.
- SO3: Identify the variables influencing young people's perceptions of sending and receiving hate speech in the MMO.
- SO4: Profile young people concerning hate speech in the MMO.

The purpose of this study was to confirm the following hypotheses:

- H1. Age, education level, ideological orientation, time spent online, perception of disinhibition in the environment, and gender are among the main factors shaping young people's perceptions of the presence of hate speech messages.
- H2. Age affects the perception, sending, and receiving of hate messages, level of education, ideological orientation, time spent, perception of disinhibition in the environment, and gender of young people involved in this scenario.
- H3. Being a bystander to hate speech messages makes young people more likely to become potential perpetrators in digital scenarios.

This study was the result of quasi-experimental and quantitative research. The data analyzed were obtained from a survey of 51 questions, organized into six thematic blocks:

- Sociodemographic profile (eight questions).
- MMO gaming habits (six questions) were based on research conducted by the Spanish Video Game Association (AEVI, 2022).
- The presence of hate speech, incitement, and victimization (14 questions) is based on research by Wachs and Wright (2018), Wachs et al. (2022), and Wright, Wachs and Guadix (2021).
- Concealment strategies (seven questions) were based on the studies by Wachs and Wright (2018).
- Toxic disinhibition (four questions), following Udris (2014).
- Sexism and violence against female users (12 questions) were based on Donoso, Rubio and Vilà (2018).

The study population was comprised of young people aged 16–29 years in Spain who had engaged in multiplayer video games, either actively or passively, 12 months before completing this survey.

The study used a probabilistic, stratified random sample by sex, age, and young residents in each city and autonomous community of the country's sociopolitical composition, according to the National Institute of Statistics (2022). Sampling units were contacted and selected from a database of panellists matching the population's characteristics with voluntary participation.

The final instrument had a reliability index of $\alpha=0.718$ (Cronbach's alpha). This index was obtained after adjustments from a pilot study conducted in September 2023, which included 60 respondents similar to the population of interest, equivalent to 4% of the total population sample used in this study ($n=1,496$, with $e=\pm 2.5$, and $1-\alpha=95\%$).

The final sample comprised 1,436 young people, with $e=\pm 2.5$, and $1-\alpha=95\%$, who completed the survey between October and November 2023. The participants' characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Some of the items (based on a 10-point Likert scale, with 1 being strongly disagree and 10 being strongly agree) included in this study are as follows (mean and median values in parentheses):

- P1. Frequency of playing multiplayer online video games (6.1; 6.0).
- P3. Frequency of seeing offensive messages (4.4; 4.0).
- P4. Frequency of sending offensive messages (1.7; 1.0).
- P5. Frequency of having personally received offensive messages (3.0; 2.0).
- P7. If you have seen these offensive messages, do you report them? (1.8, 2.0).
- P8. Frequency of concealing one's identity when playing games (4.2; 4.0).
- P9. Frequency of changing personal characteristics during gaming (3.3; 2.0).
- P10. It is okay to insult others because it is anonymous (2.5; 1.0).
- P11. It is easy to insult others because there are no repercussions (5.8; 6.0)
- P12. There are no rules; you can do whatever you want. (3.2; 2.0).
- P13. Insulting others is not a bullying, harassment, or hate. (2.5; 1.0).

After data collection, the following analyses were performed:

- A t-test was used to analyze the clusters generated using the k-means algorithm (Rai, 2019). The k-means algorithm groups data into k clusters by calculating similarities (Lantz, 2019), assigning each data point to the closest cluster, and adjusting the centroids to optimize clustering. The Dunn index (Gil, 2021) was used to calculate the optimal number of clusters (k) and to evaluate the clustering quality by maximizing the separation between clusters and minimizing dispersion within them. Values of k between 2 and 15 were tested, with k=12 yielding the best result and reaching a Dunn

index of 0.1980. This indicates that the clusters formed were compact and well-separated, effectively identifying groups of young people with similar behaviours in MMO.

- The Mean Decrease Accuracy (MDA) and Mean Decrease Gini (MDG) were calculated using a random forest algorithm to determine the significance of the investigated variables. The MDA measures the extent to which the average accuracy of the predictive model decreases when a variable is eliminated. The higher the number, the more important is the dependent variable, with responses to P3, P4, and P5 selected in each case. The MDG measures impurities in a dataset, testing the extent to which the impurity of the predictive model decreases. Higher MDA and MDG values indicated that each variable was more important in determining the overall model predicting the response to P3, P4, or P5. These metrics provide insight into the importance of each variable in the accuracy of a machine-learning model and the predictive power of the results (Lantz, 2019).

All calculations and figures were performed using R software, with the "Rattle" interface in R used to assist with the calculations (Williams, 2011).

Results and discussion

Figure 1 summarizes the profile of the young people surveyed: 1) average age of 23 years, 2) average college-level education, 3) regular MMO players, 4) medium or medium-high socioeconomic backgrounds, and 5) predominantly heterosexual and center-left ideologies.

Regarding SO1, the data showed that most respondents (over 60%) had a low-to-moderate perception of hate speech in these digital environments, whether targeted at other players or themselves. Players are perceived to be more likely to experience this for racial, religious, sexual, and ideological reasons. Most of the hate speeches witnessed were directed

at Islam (76%), people of African descent (82%), Arabs (48%), people with left-wing ideological leanings (48%), feminists (52%), and players who supported or identified as transgender (47%). Most respondents did not see themselves as active promoters of hate, with over 80% stating that they did not engage in hate speech while playing the MMO. In addition, 55.4% took a passive stance in response to such incidents.

Respondents perceived that individuals who experienced hate speech often could not recognize the violence (64%) and should not remain silent about it (71.9%). More than half were familiar with reporting procedures (57.4%) and confident in the platform's ability to control this activity (68.2%). This occurs when most agree with the need for norms (>70%) and their ability to recognize hate speech (>80%). There was also the perception that writing messages without repercussions was easy (>60%).

By applying the Random Forest algorithm, we can verify how the variables determine the perception of the presence, sending, and receiving of hate messages (SO2 and SO3), as listed in Table 2.

- Regarding the perceived presence of hate speech, the variables included sending hate speech messages (P4), not reporting such messages (P7), stating no repercussions for insulting others (P11), and considering insults as harassment (P13) and ideology (S4).
- Three main factors influenced the perception of sending hate messages: receiving messages (P5), the perceived importance of anonymous sending (P10), and young people's tendency to change identity features when gaming (P9).
- Receiving hate speech messages was determined by the following variables: disinhibition of sending messages (P4), failure to report them (P7), identity alteration (P9), concealment of identity (P8), and disinhibition associated with anonymous sending (P10).

To achieve SO4, we profiled different types of individuals. They were grouped according to the respondents' natural and social variables based on the survey answers. We developed a machine-learning model using a k-means algorithm (k=12). Table 3 shows the scores that defined the 12 groups, ranked according to the score for P3, which asked if they had encountered hate messages while playing online video games.

Analyzing the scores in Table 3, we identified four large groups with distinct characteristics. These groups are defined by their behaviour in MMO and their perceptions of hate speech in these digital environments.

- Groups with a tendency to be perpetrators:
 - Group 1 (6.32% of the total sample) had the highest exposure to hate speech in MMO. Its members are the speech's major recipients and senders and prefer anonymity. They spend more time gaming and are indifferent to norms that can moderate violent behavior in MMO. They typically self-identify as having medium-high or high socioeconomic status, college or university education, an average age of 24 years, and do not identify as either left- or right-wing. While most participants were Spanish, there was greater nationality diversity than in other groups.
 - Group 9 (9.48% of the sample) comprised young people aged 24 years with a high school to university education identified as right-wing and with medium or medium-low socioeconomic backgrounds. This is the second group most likely to send hate messages while holding moderate opinions on the repercussions and importance of these messages. After Group 1, they are most likely to use the lack of rules or repercussions as justification and are more likely to reveal their identity than the other groups.
- Groups with a tendency to be individuals who experienced hate speech:

- Group 6 (9.48%) had a lower educational and socioeconomic background (medium-low), was defined as ideologically centre-right, and admitted to spending much time playing MMO. In this situation, members are likely to be aware of their level of hate. They did not actively engage with other players but were among the groups receiving hate speech.
- Group 2 (7.22%) had a higher perception of hate speech in MMO and was characterized by older age (26.4 years). They were identified as having a medium-high or high socioeconomic status and university education. They are more left-leaning, ideologically diverse, and sexually oriented. They recognize the lack of norms in video games for messaging and are among the most targeted personally, though rarely perpetrated. Unlike the previous group, they played frequently, without excessive screen time.
- Groups 4 (3.16%) and 7 (9.71%) consisted mainly of male participants who spent a lot of time gaming, with an average ages of 25.9 and 21.8 years, respectively. Their educational level ranged from high school to university, and they were ideologically identified as more center-left. While aware of hate speech during gaming and having occasionally experienced it, neither group actively sent hate messages. Both groups believed that spreading hate was wrong.
- Groups with a tendency to be bystanders:
 - Group 3 (11.06%) reported spending the most time playing MMO. It is the youngest group (\bar{x} =19.4 years), has a medium or medium-high socioeconomic background, and an educational level of senior high school. This group is aware of the hate in MMO but neither sends nor receives them. Members conceal their identities and recognize that sending insults and hate speech is incorrect. This group is diverse in terms of sexual orientation, ideologically the center-left.

- Groups 11 and 12 (9.48% and 8.35%) had the lowest perception of hate messages. They are young (20–22 years) and are identified as center-right and left-wing individuals. Both groups were sexually diverse, with a higher prevalence among women. This profile represents those who spend the least time gaming. They negatively perceive hate speech; however, it is doubtful whether MMO can suppress it.
- Group 5 (9.48%) mainly included female participants with an average age of 23 years, medium socioeconomic background, and university education. Members change their characteristics and identities when playing an MMO. They were very aware of hate speech messages in this digital environment and perceived themselves as emitting the least hate. This group also expressed significant dissatisfaction with the lack of repercussions.
- Groups 8 (4.51%) and 10 (11.74%) represented profiles of young people with medium or medium-high socioeconomic backgrounds but were not active gamers. The average age is 24.7 and 26.7 years, respectively. There was no gender predominance, and most members were university-educated. They perceive low-hate speech in the MMO and claim that they do not receive or send it. Group 8 members were more likely to conceal their identities, whereas Group 10 members were more aware of the lack of repercussions of using hate speech. Both groups believed that hate speech was unacceptable in these virtual environments.

This study found that many young people had a medium-low perception of exposure to hate messages in MMO (SO1). This perception occurs within a digital context that utilizes the socialization capacity of these environments and the sense of belonging from the "gaming experience," as noted by Koehler, Fiebig and Jugl (2022). Consequently, many users seemed unaware of hate speech, contrary to Cáceres-Zapatero, Brändle, and Paz-Rebollo's (2023)

observations. This can be attributed to the MMO's ability to normalize certain narratives due to the serial nature of video game stories, making expressions of hate toward specific users, especially those from certain racial, religious, sexual, and ideological groups, more appealing and easily spread (Leitch, 2023). Many members perceive a favourable framework for spreading radicalizing narratives integral to their actions within the game's playful scenario.

This observation suggests that MMO should be considered an environment where violence appears normalized, as scholars like Costello, Rukus, and Hawdon (2019) indicate. This perspective necessitates considering MMO as a potential space for propagating such expressions, given the anonymity and global reach that makes them attractive for legitimizing narratives associated with extremist ideological groups (Aguerri, Santisteban & Miró-Llinares, 2023; Wells et al., 2023). This phenomenon is particularly relevant in understanding the growing interest these platforms have generated in seeking better regulatory mechanisms, aiming to balance freedom of expression, economic interests, public values, user rights protection, and the need to mitigate content that may facilitate the proposed normalization scenario (Cammaerts & Mansell, 2020; Meissner, 2022).

Participants acknowledged the impunity framework's predominance in the MMO, corroborating findings from studies by Wachs et al. (2022) and Donoso, Rubio and Vilà (2018). This occurs despite young people recognizing behavioural norms in these environments and perceiving themselves as capable of distinguishing between violent and non-violent messages.

The analysis reveals that young individuals in Spain neither recognize nor value national regulatory initiatives nor platform moderation policies. These measures are ineffective in mitigating hate messages in MMO environments. Developing collaborative and holistic approaches to new regulatory models that effectively address this issue is imperative.

These approaches must tackle the multiple challenges highlighted by scholars like Popiel (2022), Mezei (2022), Kokshagina, Reinecke and Karanasios (2023), and Trachtman (2023).

This scenario indicates that most young individuals do not perceive themselves as perpetrators. However, as witnesses adopt a passive stance, it potentially places recipients of hate-based messages in positions of increased vulnerability. This vulnerability is generated by the perceived impunity of perpetrators and those who, despite having the capacity to intervene, refrain from doing so. This scenario presents conditions conducive to increased radicalization through a negative observational learning environment, which may result in individuals emulating behaviours promoted by perpetrators of hate speech (Nakawake & Kobayashi, 2022).

Therefore, these scenarios appear conducive to increased aggression and decreased prosocial behaviour (Greitemeyer, 2022). Beyond the low levels of perception of the presence, transmission, and reception of hate messages in MMO, the results associated with SO2 and SO3 elucidate how this perception is determined by the active condition of young people in receiving or transmitting violent messages and by factors associated with their relationship to this environment (level of play, degree of identity concealment, or transformation), the sense of impunity within these digital contexts, and the normalization of violent message usage. This scenario is also influenced by sex and socioeconomic background status. These findings partially support H1 and H2, as educational level and age do not appear to influence the perception, transmission, and reception of hate messages in MMO. However, the ideological orientation that young people acknowledge and variables, such as concealment and disinhibition, are important factors to consider when addressing this issue.

This reaffirms the need to critically examine the moderation and regulation of messaging channels concerning anonymity. This aligns with Brown and Hennis's (2019)

recommendations to sanction violent language and promote those combating it. Interventions should prioritize the youngest age groups and individuals across all backgrounds, emphasizing males. Training in external institutional environments, such as educational contexts, can create complementary spaces that address hate manifestations (Struck, 2019). This approach could mitigate perpetrators' proliferation by developing recognition, prevention, confrontation, and combat skills, potentially extending beyond MMO to other contexts.

Following Wachs and Wright (2018), Wells et al. (2023), and others, young individuals are classified into three categories (witnesses, perpetrators, and those who experienced hate speech). It identifies subgroups within these categories and adds new dimensions to youth participation in Spain's MMO phenomenon. This finding highlights the complexity of categorizing young individuals as they form smaller clusters with distinct characteristics. It challenges hypothesis H3, contradicting Wachs and Wright (2018), as it does not observe witnesses transforming into perpetrators but indicates that some who experienced hate speech with a specific profile tend to become future perpetrators. This aligns with Nakawake and Kobayashi (2022) and Greitmeyer (2022), suggesting that helplessness experienced by hate speech victims may lead to considering MMO, where toxic behaviours are prevalent (Aguerri, Santisteban and Miró-Llinares, 2023). This environment may facilitate negative observational learning over prosocial behaviours. Hate speech victims may emulate negative behaviours initially directed toward them. These individuals employ identity concealment strategies and share active video game participation characteristics, as Nogueira-López et al. (2023) noted. This behaviour may contribute to continued exposure to hate messages, increasing anxiety, impulsiveness, and social skill deficits (Planells, 2020).

Conclusions

Despite the limitations of the quantitative research approach, the data (young participants' perceptions) and scope (the Spanish case) lead us to posit the necessity for companies and regulators to promote actions aimed at content moderation and altering the perception of impunity among young people. This change is crucial to impede the normalization of violence and hatred, which manifest more frequently in digital environments. This is significant considering that action, role-playing, and adventure games with substantial violence dominate the top 20 best-selling video games in 2022 in Spain (AEVI, 2022), including titles such as God of War Ragnarök, Grand Theft Auto V, and Horizon Forbidden West.

This analysis visualizes the distinct profiles of young people in Spain in gaming scenarios. This information is valuable for designing programs to educate the group about hate speech's negative impacts and foster empathy and respect in digital environments. Based on this study, initiatives can be implemented through educational and preventive programs.

It is necessary to strengthen public policies in line with the introductory section and discussions in this work, as pointed out by Cusumano, Gawer, and Yoffie (2021), Schlesinger (2022) and Fletcher (2023), to promote a safer digital environment for young people through collaboration among governments, platforms, and non-governmental organizations. These partnerships can aid in developing awareness campaigns and regulatory frameworks to combat the use of MMO and other digital spaces to promote hate, normalize such expressions, and legitimize extremist narratives, especially against vulnerable groups. This is crucial given the MMO anonymity, perceived impunity, and global reach that facilitate these harmful activities.

The results of this study underscore the need to advance proposals by authors such as DeCook et al. (2022). It emphasizes implementing measures beyond punitive actions to promote structural changes and reduce hate speech in digital environments. These measures

should foster shared responsibility among agents and ensure greater transparency in MMO moderation actions to control the interactions that promote hate.

A comprehensive approach could include developing multilevel training and communication programs for young users and social actors such as families and educational agents. These programs should provide basic knowledge regarding hate message proliferation (Arce-García et al., 2024) and teach students how to identify and combat them in digital environments. They should also promote an understanding of the fundamental rights and democratic values these platforms must protect beyond their economic interests or use freedom of expression to justify self-regulation.

The results indicate that young people perceive these platforms as spaces of impunity that promote hate globally. Addressing these problems collaboratively and ethically is crucial, prioritizing social well-being and democratic sustainability in the digital environment.

This study has the potential to open new research lines and broaden the scope of this topic. New studies must delve deeper into this approach to develop a practical regulatory, moderating, and social framework against hate speech in MMO. These should contribute to understanding key aspects: how young users understand and respond to social norms; how to encourage upstander roles; and identifying predominant types and intensity of hate messages, sender profiles, and spread strategies. This represents a promising path for future research.

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Tables

Table 1. Socio-demographic profile of the sample

Variables	N	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Socioeconomic backgrounds*	1436	100	1	7	3.2779	1.66625
	Levels				%	
	1. Households with a monthly income > €3,005				15.6	
	2. €2,452 - €3,005				23.6	
	3. €2,146 - €2,451				16.9	
	4. €1,603 - €2,145				22.1	
	5. €1,313 - €1,602				7.5	
	6. €745 - €1,312				11.6	
	7. < €745				2.6	
Level of education	N	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	1436	100	1	8	4.99	1.320
	Levels				%	
	1. No formal education (Incomplete elementary education)				0.8	
	2. Elementary school. (Elementary school diploma, EGB (General Basic Education) Stage 1, approx. 10 years old)				0.8	
	3. High school. Phase 1 (High school diploma, or EGB Stage 2, 1 st /2 nd year of ESO [Obligatory Secondary Education] (Phase 1), up to 14 years old)				4.2	
	4. High school. Phase 2 (FP (Vocational Training) Levels I and II, 3 rd /4 th Year of ESO (Phase 2), 1 st /2 nd year Spanish Baccalaureate, up to 18 years old)				44.3	

	5. Tertiary. Phase 1 (Equivalent to 3 years of technical engineering training, University Schools, Technical Engineers, among others)				10.4	
	6. Tertiary, Undergraduate degree. Phase 2 (University degree, higher degrees, faculties, higher technical schools, among others)				22.5	
	7. Tertiary. Graduate. (Masters)				16.4	
	8. Tertiary. Graduate. (Doctorate)				0.6	
Age	N	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	1436	100	16	29	23.78	3.339
Gender	N^	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	1422	100	1	2	1.49	0.500
	Category					%
	1. Men					51
	2. Women					49
Nationality	N^^	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	1063	100	1	3	1.16	0.507
	Category					%
	1. Spanish					90.1
	2. Dual nationality (Spanish and other)					3.8
3. Other nationality (not Spanish)					6.1	
Sexual Orientation	N^^^	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	1026	100	1	2	1.21	0.413
	Category					%
	A range of sexual orientations, with a majority identifying as heterosexual					78.2
	LGBTI+					21.8

Ideological orientation**	N+	%	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
	935	100	1	10	4.48	2.436

* The classification of socioeconomic backgrounds was based on criteria established by the General Media Study (2018).

** The classification was based on the scale used by the Sociological Research Center (CIS, 2020).

Missing data: ^=14. ^=373. ^=410. +=501.

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Table 2. Random Forest with respect to P3, P4, and P5

Variable	P3		P4		P5	
	MDA	MDG	MDA	MDG	MDA	MDG
EST	2.47	21.01	2.75	5.87	0.87	12.3
F1	2.09	33.04	0.39	8.86	0.04	20.27
F2	2.61	10.98	4.17	2.82	3.28	6.53
F3	3.2	37.44	-1.32	9.22	-1.89	21.63
P1	13.6	27.15	5.95	8.56	17.17	25.76
P10	15.27	19.16	13.09	17.74	18.81	19.06
P11	34.23	44.59	-0.29	7.48	2.54	18.06
P12	13.61	22.27	3.44	10.21	15.88	20.22
P13	32.98	24.39	6.02	13.76	5.35	12.58
P3	13.15	11.28	9.92	9.87	50.2	56.68
P4	52.91	55.5	21.54	20.07	29.16	23.94
P7	49.82	53.39	-1.19	3.7	22.24	18.97
P8	14.96	25.99	7.05	7.52	19.34	23.94
P9	16.99	26.18	10.37	8.44	23.52	27.22
S1	12.63	7.51	-1.04	1.8	-1.82	3.4
S3	11.79	13.22	2.44	3.78	-0.04	8.64
S4	25.28	34.7	-0.85	8.38	2.18	18.24
SE	1.37	26.63	1.96	8.28	2.51	16.56

Table 3. K-means groups (k=12), ranked from highest to lowest value for P3

N. °	S E	E S T	F1	F 2	P 1	P 3	P 4	P 5	P 7	P 8	P 9	P1 0	P1 1	P1 2	P1 3	S 1	S 3	S 4	Size
1	2. 5	5. 6	23 .9	1. 2	9. 1	7. 9	7. 4	7. 6	7. 6	7. 9	7. 0	7. 5	7. 3	7. 4	7. 4	1. 3	1. 6	4. 9	6.32 %
2	2. 6	5. 5	26 .4	1. 3	7. 2	7. 8	1. 9	6. 1	1. 5	6. 2	2. 9	3. 2	8. 5	4. 7	2. 0	1. 1	1. 8	3. 7	7.22 %
3	3. 5	4. 2	19 .4	1. 5	8. 9	6. 9	1. 1	3. 0	1. 5	7. 9	5. 3	1. 7	2. 9	2. 2	1. 5	1. 3	1. 9	4. 6	11.1 %
4	2. 8	5. 1	25 .9	1. 2	8. 6	6. 7	1. 8	5. 0	1. 3	2. 4	1. 7	2. 2	2. 4	1. 8	1. 6	1. 1	1. 3	4. 0	3.16 %
5	3. 0	4. 9	23 .0	1. 8	6. 0	6. 6	1. 1	4. 1	1. 6	8. 0	8. 0	1. 5	8. 5	2. 9	1. 8	1. 1	2. 0	3. 8	9.48 %
6	3. 7	4. 0	20 .0	1. 1	8. 1	6. 3	2. 8	4. 7	1. 5	3. 2	3. 0	4. 5	6. 3	5. 0	4. 5	1. 2	1. 2	5. 8	9.48 %
7	3. 9	4. 5	21 .8	1. 2	8. 3	5. 9	1. 4	3. 4	1. 6	1. 9	1. 4	1. 9	7. 8	1. 4	1. 8	1. 2	1. 3	3. 9	9.71 %
8	3. 5	5. 0	24 .7	1. 5	4. 3	4. 8	1. 3	2. 5	1. 9	6. 3	5. 6	1. 5	2. 9	2. 3	1. 3	1. 3	1. 4	4. 0	4.51 %
9	3. 8	4. 8	24 .0	1. 4	5. 5	4. 8	3. 5	4. 1	1. 8	4. 9	4. 5	5. 8	5. 4	6. 1	5. 7	1. 2	1. 5	6. 0	9.48 %
10	2. 6	5. 7	26 .7	1. 5	4. 8	4. 3	1. 1	1. 9	1. 8	1. 8	1. 6	1. 7	7. 8	3. 5	2. 2	1. 2	1. 4	4. 3	11.74 %
11	3. 0	4. 2	19 .9	1. 5	4. 1	3. 9	1. 1	1. 9	1. 8	4. 6	2. 2	1. 5	7. 3	2. 8	1. 7	1. 1	2. 0	5. 2	9.48 %
12	3. 4	4. 8	22 .5	1. 6	4. 1	3. 6	1. 4	2. 0	2. 0	1. 6	1. 3	1. 5	2. 2	1. 8	1. 5	1. 2	1. 9	3. 5	8.35 %

The scores represent the mean values for each variable based on the data from the possible responses to each question.

Figure 1. Distribution of the variables

SE=Socioeconomic backgrounds; EST=Educational level; F1=Age; F2=Gender; P1=Frequency of playing MMO; SI=Participants residing in Spain; S3=Sexual orientation; S4=Ideological orientation.